

DEVELOPMENT OF A DIGITAL-BASED TEACHING MATERIAL MODEL FOR CIREBON LEGEND TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

The scarcity of supplementary teaching materials that teachers and students can use in learning the literary of Cirebon Legend in the digital era gives rise to the urgency to develop digital-based supplementary teaching materials of fantasy texts following the Merdeka (Independence) Curriculum. This research aimed to create digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend texts as an application that serves as supplementary teaching materials for seventh-grade students in Junior High Schools (SMP). This research used the Research and Development (R&D) model, according to Borg and Gall. The components of teaching materials include four aspects: content aspect, presentation aspect, language and readability aspect, and graphic (visual) aspect. These aspects were used in the validity test by expert lecturers and teachers and in students' response questionnaires. This research found that the digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend texts for seventh-grade students received positive responses and are eligible for further use as supplementary teaching materials.

KEYWORDS

teaching materials, Cirebon legend, digital

INTRODUCTION

Teaching materials are one of the instructional tools designed by educators to facilitate the learning process. These efforts aim to create an enjoyable learning atmosphere that interests students. Additionally, teaching materials can be used as supporting materials based on specific learning outcomes and objectives.

Mascita (2021:51-62) explains that the development of teaching materials is not only about determining the essence, depth, scope, sequence of material presentation and treatment of teaching materials but also about how these teaching materials contribute to learning and help students understand the content explained in the curriculum. Therefore, teachers must prepare teaching materials to enhance the qualifications standards, basic skills, indicators, and curriculum topics.

The education curriculum in Indonesia has great hopes for generating Pancasila students, according to the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture for 2020-2024. Pancasila students are lifelong learners who possess global competencies, behave in faith, devote themselves to God Almighty, and have noble character. Moreover, they embrace global diversity, work together, demonstrate independence, think critically, and are creative (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2020).

Within the Merdeka Curriculum, there is a term known as Learning Outcomes. Learning Outcomes (LO) are the learning competencies that students must achieve at each phase.

For the Indonesian Language subject, the targeted learning outcomes for seventh-grade Junior High School students fall within Phase D. As an example, one of the learning outcomes in the context of narrative texts is that students can analyze and interpret information in the form of ideas, thoughts, feelings, perspectives, directions, or messages accurately from audiovisual and aural fantasy texts in the form of monologues, dialogues, and speeches. These learning outcomes emphasize that students are encouraged to develop receptive listening skills. In other words, students are trained to absorb, understand, and interpret the information they hear effectively, enabling them to respond to the speaker. Processes involved in listening include focused listening, identifying, understanding opinions, and interpreting language based on the context behind the speech. Components developed in listening include sensitivity to language sounds, sign systems, vocabulary, language structure (grammar), meaning, and metacognition.

One text of fantasy imbued with local culture is legend texts. As a teaching material for fantasy texts, legend texts manifest written oral traditions. An analysis of the Legend of Cirebon, employing Koentjaraningrat's theory (2009) by Mukmin (2020), reveals that the cultural values of Cirebon encompass five fundamental issues, namely the essence of life, the essence of work, human position, human-nature relationship, and human-human relationship. Therefore, teaching the Legend of Cirebon is expected to instill the cultural values embedded within the legend text.

Based on the above explanation, it can be concluded that the Legend of Cirebon can be developed as a fantasy text teaching material for seventh-grade Junior High School students to embody their Pancasila profile.

Digital teaching materials can visualize storylines, objects, and subjects in animations. This aligns with the competency needs of 21st-century teachers or educators who have entered the digital era, where they can motivate and inspire student learning and creativity, design and develop learning experiences and assessments in the digital era, and serve as role models for learning and working in the digital era, promoting and exemplifying responsibility in the digital society. Adams Becker et al. (2017) argue that technology is not an adequate solution but rather a support for more effective teaching and learning approaches. Technology should be based on progressive pedagogy and models encouraging greater student engagement and performance. This explanation is in line with the opinion of Anwar et al (2021: 162) that new technological advances can integrate the physical, digital and natural worlds that have affected all scientific disciplines.

To complete the data obtained in this field, the researchers correlate it with previous research by Setiyawati (2022) entitled Development of Canva Application-Based Illustrated Folklore Teaching Materials to Improve the Learning Outcomes of Fourth-Grade Students. This research states that the teaching materials developed are suitable for use as Indonesian language teaching materials for fourth-grade students. The percentage of expert validation results and student responses were deemed effective in enhancing the learning outcomes of fourth-grade students at State Elementary School (SDN) 1 of North Bengkulu. Wisudawati, W. and Sumardi, A. (2023) conducted similar research titled Development of a Flipbook-Based Fairy Tale Module Laden with Pancasila Values. In this research, a text module of fairy tales laden with Pancasila values was developed based on a flipbook. The results of the feasibility test of students' responses were 98% in the assessment of material experts, and the feasibility level was 97.50%.

Further research on folklore was conducted by Kusmana et al. (2021) with the title Development of Teaching Materials for Fable Texts Laden with Local Wisdom for Indonesian Language Learning. Presenting learning materials visually through videos is more engaging and effective in shaping students' character.

Meanwhile, Khuzaemah and Ummi (2019) conducted research entitled Development of Skill-Oriented Fable Texts and Short Story Teaching Materials in which the teaching materials developed were in the form of modules, and their implementation followed a scientific approach. By applying the scientific approach, learning can align with the principles of effective teaching.

In the Dieksis Journal, Komariah (2018) researched the development of teaching materials entitled, Development of Brass Folklore Teaching Materials Integrated with Character Values in Learning Literature Appreciation in Middle School. This research develops teaching materials for Kuningan folklore based on character education in the form of Student Work Sheets, considered suitable for inculcating student character values.

Based on the explanations above, the researchers researched Cirebon's local legends to be used as supplementary teaching materials for students. Therefore, this research was entitled Development of a Digital-Based Teaching Material Model for Cirebon Legend Texts with the following research questions: (1) How is the feasibility analysis of Cirebon Legend texts as supplementary teaching materials? (2) How do experts assess the feasibility of the digital-based Cirebon Legend text teaching materials for seventh-grade Junior High School students? (3) How are the seventh-grade Junior High School students' trial outcomes of the digital-based Cirebon Legend text teaching materials?

Figure 1. Results of VOSviewer Analysis

Based on the results of the VOSviewer analysis, the novelty of this research lies in developing digital-based legend materials with an application model for seventh-grade Junior High School students. This teaching material development is not only in the form of text but also includes images, animations, and animated videos of legends so that the presentation is more varied and engaging, avoiding boredom. Furthermore, digital teaching materials are accommodated by an application that can be accessed on smartphones. Additionally, four levels of learning are considered in the development of the legend text instructional materials, namely explanation of contextual construction, modeling, leadership (co-construction), and independence (independent construction).

RESEARCH METHODS

This research used the research and development (R&D) method according to the Borg and Gall development model (Borg & Gall, 1983: 775). The Borg & Gall development model provides systematic guidance on how researchers ensure that the products they design meet appropriate standards.

The first stage of this development was research and data collection, including various aspects such as needs analysis, literature review, small-scale research, and value aspects. In this phase, the researchers divided the discussion into material selection, school selection, and needs analysis. The researchers prepared instruments to obtain data directly in the field during data collection. The instruments consisted of observation, questionnaires, and interviews. Then, the product development stage followed. At this point, the relevant data analysis results were obtained. This research resulted in Cirebon Legend products in the form of digital application-based teaching materials integrated with cultural values. The Cirebon Legend contains five fundamental problems to implement the profile of Pancasila students. Moreover, the development of teaching materials was carried out by studying specific literature for previously planned subjects.

The validity test of this product was conducted to determine its usability and implementation. This phase occurred after the product design was developed. At the validity test stage, the product was reviewed by the teaching material experts and subject teachers who would implement it in the classroom. Product revisions were made if the initial validity test results indicated the need to improve the original product. Based on the validity results, these improvements were likely to be made more than once to create the final product design (mockup) ready for broader testing. However, product development was discontinued if no weaknesses were found during the experiment.

The aspects considered in the validity test and trial of digital-based legend text teaching materials include (1) content aspect; (2) presentation aspect; (3) language and readability aspect; and (4) graphic (visual) aspect. Besides, a feedback column was provided for experts to give comments and suggestions regarding any deficiencies found in the teaching materials.

According to Akbar (2013: 40-41), the validity of teaching materials is determined by the alignment of empirical validation results and predefined validity criteria. The validation criteria table for digital-based legend text teaching materials for seventh-grade Junior High School students is as follows:

Table 1. Validity Criteria for Teaching Materials

No.	Validity Criteria	Validity Levels
1	81.00 % - 100.00%	Highly valid or can be used without revisions
2	61.00 % - 80.00 %	Fairly valid or can be used with minor revisions
3	41.00 % - 60.00 %	Less valid or not recommended for use because it needs major revision
4	00.00 % - 20.00%	Highly invalid or cannot be used

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first stage of this research, entitled Development of Digital-Based Teaching Materials for Cirebon Legend Texts, involved data collection, including the measurement of needs, literature review, small-scale research, and considerations regarding the value, material selection, school selection and needs analysis. Subsequently, the researchers analyzed six legend texts, which were sourced from two books entitled Kalijaga, Kanoman, Klayan, Ciawigajah, Nyi Mas Gandasari, and Panjunan. The analysis results indicated that all the legend texts were suitable to be used as legend text teaching materials for seventh-grade Junior High School students because they had complete structures. Although the legend texts did not strictly adhere to all grammatical rules, it does not matter as no regulations require them to include all aspects of grammatical rules.

The second stage involved teaching materials development. Based on expert opinions from Kosasih (2020: 255), Heinrich et al. (1996: 204-205), Alessi & Trollip (2001: 48), and Romiszowski (1986: 406-407) regarding the principles of digital teaching materials, the researchers concluded that the development of digital teaching materials requires an evaluation of their suitability. The components evaluated include the content, presentation, language, and readability aspects and graphic (visual) aspects. Therefore, the researchers used these four components as references in developing teaching materials.

In developing digital-based legend text teaching materials, the researchers prepared materials aligned with the four learning elements. The materials were then described based on learning outcomes. Moreover, the formulation of digital teaching material titles was adjusted according to the determination of the learning texts listed in the main teaching materials used, namely the Indonesian Language of Merdeka Curriculum textbook issued by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology for seventh-grade Junior High School's Indonesian language subject.

Figure 2. Development Model of Legend Text Teaching Materials

Then, after the product development stage, the researcher conducted a product validity test to determine the feasibility of testing a product on a small scale.

Figure 3. Combined Results of Validations from Experts and Subject Teachers

The figure above shows that the validation questionnaire yielded a result of 93.75% from expert lecturers and subject teachers regarding the digital-based legend text teaching materials. The criteria based on the obtained scores indicate that the digital-based legend text teaching material is highly valid. This means the designed digital-based legend text teaching material can be used without revisions.

Furthermore, the researchers trialed the digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon legend texts to the seventh-grade students at State Junior High School 1 of Cirebon City. The trial was performed in a small group involving ten students from the seventh grade. To ensure an effective trial, the researchers chose to carry out the trial within the learning activities.

During the trial of the digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon legend texts at State Junior High School 1 of Cirebon City, the researchers obtained data in the form of student questionnaires and interview results. The results of questionnaires and interviews were further analyzed using the descriptive-analytic method, namely describing the data in a narrative form and interpreting their meanings.

Table 2. Results of Student Response Questionnaires

No.	Subjects	Scores of Student Response Questionnaires
1	Student 1	97.5
2	Student 2	92.5
3	Student 3	95
4	Student 4	95
5	Student 5	97.5
6	Student 6	92.5
7	Student 7	95
8	Student 8	97.5
9	Student 9	95
10	Student 10	97.5
Total Questionnaire Scores		955
Maximum Questionnaire Scores		1000

The researchers then calculated the filled student response questionnaires based on the data. The total score obtained was 955 out of a maximum of 1000, resulting in a feasibility percentage of 95.5%. The questionnaire results indicate that students can effectively use the digital-based teaching material of Cirebon legend texts during learning.

Interviews with students were also conducted to reinforce the primary data obtained from the results of student response questionnaires regarding the digital-based legend text teaching materials for seventh-grade Junior High School students. The students expressed that the Cirebon legend texts presented in this application were highly suitable for assisting their learning activities. They found the interface appealing and engaging and the language easy to understand. They hope this application can be widely disseminated to various schools, particularly in the Cirebon region, so that it is widely known by students and used as teaching material in schools.

CONCLUSION

This research, entitled Development of Digital-Based Teaching Materials for Cirebon Legend Texts, resulted in an analysis and description of the feasibility of using Cirebon legend texts as teaching materials, the validity test results of digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend texts by two experts, as well as the results of limited trials of digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend texts to seventh-grade Junior High School students. The researchers only used four of the six legend texts analyzed in the developed teaching materials: Kalijaga, Klayan, Ciawigajah, and Nyi Mas Gandasari.

Based on this research, Cirebon legend texts are suitable as teaching materials, considering their structure and language. Second, the response from expert lecturers regarding the

validity of this product received a score of 94.67%, while that from Indonesian language teachers received a score of 95.85%. These scores indicate a high level of validity. Therefore, the data concludes that the digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend texts are suitable as supplementary materials for teaching fantasy texts to seventh-grade students. Third, the response from State Junior High School 1 students of Cirebon City in the limited trials of the legend text application showed an average survey score of 95.5%. Based on these results, the digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend text for seventh-grade students are considered highly valid. This evaluation indicates that students have positively received the digital-based teaching materials of Cirebon Legend texts and can continue to be used as teaching materials for learning legend text material content.

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